

Stability Constants of Mercury(II) and Beryllium(II) Complexes with 5-Substituted-uracils

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THE biological functions of nucleic acids involve the participation of metal ions. Uracil and 5-methyluracil are among the common bases derived from nucleic acids. Srivastava and Srivastava¹ studied the formation constants of Be^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes of uracil and thymine. In recent years certain synthetic substituted-uracils have found great importance in many metabolic processes, most of which are also mediated by metal ions^{2,3}. 5-Halogenated-uracils act as chemical mutagens, inhibitors of protein and nucleic acid synthesis, and are consequently cancerostatic and antiviral agents⁴. It is, therefore, of interest to gain an insight into the nature of metal complexation of 5-substituted-uracils. The present paper describes a potentiometric study of the complex formation of Be^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes of 5-substituted-uracils, namely, 5-methyluracil, 5-bromouracil, 5-iodouracil, 5-nitouracil and 5-aminouracil.

Experimental

Uracil, 5-methyluracil, 5-bromouracil, 5-iodouracil, 5-nitouracil and 5-aminouracil were of Sigma grade. HgCl₂, BeSO₄·4H₂O and all other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The solutions were prepared in double distilled CO₂-free water and metal solutions were standardised by standard methods⁵. pH measurements were made using glass-calomel electrode assembly. Bjerrum-Calvin pH-titration technique^{6,7} as used by Irving and Rossotti⁸ has been employed. The following solutions were titrated against standard carbonate-free 0.1 M KOH solution in aqueous medium: (i) 1 × 10⁻³ M HCl, (ii) 1 × 10⁻³ M HCl + 1 × 10⁻³ M ligand, and (iii) 1 × 10⁻³ M HCl + 1 × 10⁻³ M ligand + 1 × 10⁻³ M metal ion solution. In most cases, the titration could not be completed because of the separation of a solid phase before the inflexion point is reached. From the shift in pH-titration curves, values of *n*_A, *n* and *pL* were obtained using the method of Irving and Rossotti⁸.

Results and Discussion

All the ligands showed one-proton ionisation. Uracil is a pyrimidine base containing two heterocyclic nitrogen atoms at 1,3-positions and two phenolic OH groups at 2- and 4-positions. Ir and uv spectral studies have shown that uracil and 5-substituted-uracils can exist in keto form¹⁰ and thus theoretically have two ionisable protons,

but they have been observed to yield only one constant¹¹.

The basicities of the ligands were found to be in the order (Table 1), 5-nitouracil < 5-bromouracil < 5-iodouracil < uracil < 5-aminouracil < 5-methyluracil. This is expected on the basis of the order of decreasing inductive effect (electron-attracting) in atoms or group of atoms, NO₂ > Br > I > H. The increased protonation constants of 5-methyluracil and 5-aminouracil compared to uracil is explained on the basis of electron-releasing effect of methyl (inductive) and amino (resonance) groups.

In case of Hg^{II} complexes, HgCl₂ was used as metal salt. On the basis of stability constant data¹² for Hg^{II} with Cl⁻ (*K*₁ = 10^{6.79} and *K*₂ = 10^{6.48}), one might reasonably expect the ligand to have a lower affinity for Hg^{II} than does Cl⁻. Thus Hg-Cl bond remains intact in HgCl₂ during complexation with the ligands. However, the stability constant values for HgCl₂ and HgCl₂⁻ complexes are low (*K*₁ = 10^{0.86} and *K*₂ = 10^{1.00}). This suggests that various ligands used in the present study have much greater affinity for HgCl₂ compared to Cl⁻ ion. The lowest pH at which precipitation of HgCl₂ hydrolysis occurs is ≈ 8,

TABLE 1—PROTONATION CONSTANTS AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF 5-SUBSTITUTED-URACILS

Temp. = 31 ± 0.1°, μ = 0.1 M KCl

Ligand (LH)	p <i>K</i> _{LH} ^H	log <i>K</i> _{HgCl₂L} ^{HgCl₂}	log <i>K</i> _{BeL} ^{Be}
Uracil	9.17	5.04	7.41
5-Methyluracil	9.54	5.45	7.81
5-Bromouracil	7.24	3.40	5.65
5-Iodouracil	8.13	4.49	6.30
5-Nitouracil	5.67	1.90	8.80
5-Aminouracil	9.94	5.42	7.47

and also the precipitation of Hg^{II} requires a higher concentration of OH⁻ in the presence of Cl⁻ ion than other ions¹³. Therefore, there seems to be no possibility of hydroxo complexes in case of Hg^{II} complexes. The complexation equilibria may be represented as

In order to prevent the formation of products resulting from Be^{II} hydrolysis, the concentration of Be^{II} was kept low (1 mM) and the systems studied upto pH range 4.0–5.4. The lowest pH at which precipitation of Be^{II} hydroxide for 20 mM Be^{II} solution occurs¹⁴ is ≈ 6. The stability constant values (log *K*₁) increase with increasing basicity of the ligand.

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There are various possible sites on the uracil (1) for complex formation: (i) chelation between 5-substituent and 4-carbonyl, (ii) complexing on N-1, and (iii) complexing on N-3. Since the stability constant values of the uracil complexes were found to be higher than 5-bromouracil, 5-iodouracil and 5-nitouracil, this excludes the possibility of chelation involving bromo, iodo and nitro groups with 4-carbonyl groups. The possible complexing sites are now limited only to the nitrogens. For some metal ions, the stability constants of uracils are of the same order of magnitude as those of their corresponding deoxyuridines, the N-1 of which is blocked with a sugar molecule⁴. Moreover, the fact that the tendency of keto-enol tautomerism is more at N-3 than N-1 and complex formation is accompanied by the release of proton and there is an available proton on N-3 in 5-substituted uracils, makes N-3 as a complexing site most plausible. A comparison of stabilities of HgCl_2 and Be^{II} complexes show that Be^{II} complexes are more stable than those of HgCl_2 for all ligands studied. The higher stability of Be^{II} complexes may be due to smaller effective ionic radii compared to Hg^{II} . Further, Be^{II} being a hard acid tends to bond with hard bases favourably compared to soft acid Hg^{II} .

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Infrared, Thermal and X-Ray Diffraction Studies on Lanthanum Soaps

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THE methods of preparation, properties and industrial applications of alkali, alkaline-earth and transition metal soaps have been thoroughly investigated but the studies of rare earth metal soaps¹⁻⁸ have remained almost unexplored inspite of their large applications in industries. The present work deals with the characteristics of lanthanum soaps in solid state using infrared, thermal and X-ray diffraction measurements.

Experimental

Lanthanum soaps were prepared, purified and analysed by the methods described in our earlier communication¹. The results for carbon, hydrogen and metal contents were found in agreement with the theoretically calculated values.

The infrared absorption spectra were obtained with a Perkin-Elmer 577 grating spectrophotometer in the region 4000-400 cm^{-1} . The TGA was carried out at a constant heating rate of 10° min^{-1} (in a Mettler TG 50 instrument). The X-ray diffraction patterns were obtained with a Rich-Seifert 2002D diffractometer using $\text{Cu-K}\alpha$ radiation filtered by a nickel foil over the range of diffraction angle, $2\theta = 3-40^\circ$, where θ is the Bragg angle. The wavelength of radiation was 1.542 Å.

Results and Discussion

Ir spectra: The wavenumbers of important absorption maxima in the infrared spectra of lanthanum soaps (caprate and laurate) are assigned and compared with those of the corresponding fatty acids and sodium soaps. The absorption maxima near 2 660-2 650, 1 700-1 680, 1 449-1 430, 950-930, 690 and 550 cm^{-1} are associated with the localised carboxyl group of the acid molecules in the dimeric state and confirm the presence of hydrogen bonding between two molecules of fatty acid. The complete disappearance of the carbonyl frequency at 1 700 cm^{-1} in the spectra of sodium and lanthanum soaps indicates that there is a complete resonance in the two C-O bonds of the soap molecule and the group has an ionic nature. The appearance of two bands of the carboxyl group corresponding to the symmetric and anti-symmetric stretching vibrations of the carboxylate ion near 1 450-1 440 and 1 650-1 600 cm^{-1} in the spectra of sodium and lanthanum soaps instead of one band near 1 700 cm^{-1} confirms